

Puértolas-Pascual, E., & Mateus, O. (2020). A three-dimensional skeleton of Goniopholididae from the Late Jurassic of Portugal: implications for the reinforcement system of Crocodylomorpha.

In this study we describe a partially articulated model of a small neosuchian crocodylomorph from the Upper Jurassic of Portugal. The skeleton corresponds to the posterior region of the trunk and is composed of dorsal, ventral and limb osteoderms, dorsal vertebrae, torcular ribs and part of the posterior limb. The study focuses on the comparison of thermal armor (osteoderms) with the variety of neoplasms from the Jurassic, Cretaceous and current periods, providing a detailed description of this type of osteoderms. The exceptional 3D preservation of the specimen and the use of micro-computed tomography at CENIEH allows us to interpret the bone system of this organism to evaluate whether the predicted models are accurate. The support system is the set of vertebrae, osteoderms, ligaments and muscles that support the organism and are involved in its style of locomotion. The characters observed in this specimen are consistent with Goniopholididae, a family of neoplasms abundant in the majority of semi-aquatic ecosystems from the Jurassic and Cretaceous of Laurasia.

Figure. Fossil and 3D reconstruction of the osteoderms and interpretation and comparison of the different support systems in Crocodylomorpha.

